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intellectual
property
management

1996

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Foreword

ERC conducts excellent science across a wide range of subject areas and as a result has ownership and exploitation rights to a diverse range of Intellectual Property which is added to and enriched daily.

It is vital that NERC fully exploits the results of its research. To achieve this it is important that each member of staff takes an active part in the understanding and management of Intellectual Property generated from NERC funding. This will help ensure that NERC contributes to the wealth creation of the UK and through the licensing of Intellectual Property and related activities can generate additional income to support its science.

This Intellectual Property Management Handbook should assist each individual to take an active part in managing Intellectual Property: identifying, valuing, protecting and exploiting it. I commend it to you all.

John Krebs
Chief Executive

Executive Summary

This handbook describes, and informs on, Intellectual Property (IP) management and routes for exploitation. There are a number of steps involved in managing and exploiting IP; for the NERC community to strengthen its performance in this area it is important for these steps to be integrated into the organisation at all levels of programme planning and execution.

The 1993 White Paper, *Realising our potential*, the Technology Foresight Initiative and the creation of the Challenge Fund provided a focus for NERC to re-appraise its exploitation strategy and in so doing to look closely at how NERC manages its Intellectual Property.

The publication of the data management handbook in January 1996 and now this intellectual property management handbook will help each individual in the NERC community to take an active part in the effective management of NERC IP and so ensure that NERC is best placed to make a significant contribution to the Wealth Creation of the UK.

The handbook is divided into two parts: the first part describes core activities associated with IP exploitation, this includes identification, ownership, valuation, protection and mechanisms for exploitation. The second part considers management of the exploitation process: stimulation of exploitation, information and support that is available to aid exploitation and methods of finance for exploitation.

The main points on which NERC should be focusing in order to further improve its exploitation record are described in the following:

Identification

Identification of IP with potential industrial applications can be improved in several ways.

- ❖ Early consideration within each programme of potential commercial applications and possible partners at the project planning stage will raise the level of awareness of the importance of IP.
- ❖ Outputs from Technology Foresight exercises provided initial guidance about obvious user communities for specific areas of research.
- ❖ Involving scientists with industrial experience in research projects.
- ❖ Early market research or intelligence should be gathered to allow product development during the research stage which is in tune with user needs.

Ownership

Ownership of any IP must be determined. Contractual arrangements for Intellectual Property Rights from research must be secured before undertaking any research.

The difference between ownership of the Intellectual Property itself and ownership of the exploitation rights should be clearly understood by all parties and personnel. It is possible to retain ownership and control of the IP but to licence the rights to exploit it.

Exploitation

There is wide recognition that the commercial exploitation of science and technology occurs most

effectively when the process of research and discovery is in parallel with marketing and other commercial efforts; these should start early in research programmes.

- ❖ Exploitation plans should evolve by simultaneous evaluation of likely research outcomes and market potential.
- ❖ Research can be altered or supplemented as opportunities for the creation and development of commercially valuable IP become apparent.
- ❖ Wealth creating opportunities are more likely to occur when interaction between scientists, industrialists and technologists is high.

Protection

IP protection takes several different forms, some forms are automatic, whilst others must be obtained by application to the patent office. IP protection *can* be important for some IP exploitation opportunities and should be actively considered in all cases. Public dissemination of IP through a lecture or paper or any other form prior to securing patent protection will jeopardise your patent application. However, patenting is not a pre-requisite to exploit. Where patents are concerned it may be beneficial to allow an industrial partner to hold a patent as they may be better placed to defend any infringements.

Education and Training

In order that NERC can effectively manage its IP, it is important that each individual understands what Intellectual Property is and acquires an understanding of its potential value. These notes will aid this. However, to ensure that this learning process is undertaken, the responsibility for IP management should, to the extent line managers feel is relevant, be incorporated into the job description of each individual.

Successful Exploitation

A strong message which issues from these notes is the need for each individual to gain a better understanding of the commercialisation process and to be better informed about user needs. A first step to achieving this is through gaining an understanding of Intellectual Property and its importance to NERC; to gain a better awareness of what might have commercial value.

An understanding of the market place and the commercial environment is imperative to exploit IP, whether negotiating a licence agreement or estimating a value prior to selling the IP. Developing partnerships and relationships with industry can help nurture this process and will allow NERC to maximise the outcomes of its science and research for use in perhaps unforeseen applications and so ensure that products are created that will have a strong place in the market.

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Preface

These notes are aimed to be used in conjunction with Intellectual Property generated within NERC Institutes and are issued to NERC staff on that basis. The principles involved in the sound management of IP are relevant to the whole NERC research community. These guidance notes are available to members of that community on request.

This handbook is a guide only and should be used for educational purposes. It provides basic information on Intellectual Property and its exploitation and sources of information and guidance. Further information on specific aspects of IP management should be sought from your local IP Manager, Marketing Team, Industrial Liaison

Officer or NERC Technology Interaction Group in Swindon.

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Introduction

Background

Intellectual Property (IP) is the product of human thought, creativity and intellectual effort. The law recognises that the time spent in creating inventions and making discoveries is an investment which needs to be protected. The law recognises different categories of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) including patent, registered design, design right, trademark, confidential information, copyright and know-how.

Intellectual property generated by NERC manifests itself in many different forms which include data, software, innovative products and innovative processes. All NERC intellectual property, an intangible asset in itself, has the potential for commercial exploitation. These guidance notes provide basic information on the management and commercial exploitation of NERC intellectual property.

Objectives

The aim of these notes is to help in the stimulation of innovative activity by encouraging the use of NERC research to secure economic benefit. To achieve this NERC must become more competent in the identification and management of its Intellectual Property.

Structure

The notes are structured in two parts. The first part describes the various steps involved in commercial exploitation and the second part deals with issues which ensure the effective and efficient management of IP.

PART ONE: Core Activities Associated with Intellectual Property Management

The exploitation process involves a number of steps which are covered in separate chapters, these include:

- ❖ Recognising and characterising intellectual property with commercial exploitation potential.
- ❖ Identification of the ownership in order to exploit the intellectual property.
- ❖ Determining the commercial value of the intellectual property.
- ❖ Protecting intellectual property using the appropriate legal mechanisms.
- ❖ Selecting the appropriate route to the commercial market.

PART TWO: Effective Management of Intellectual Property Exploitation

Effective management of IP requires all levels within an organisation to take an active role in understanding the exploitation process by:

- ❖ Encouraging staff to participate fully in the exploitation of Intellectual Property.
- ❖ Knowing where to go to start building up market information.
- ❖ Access to appropriate levels of finance for commercial activities.

PART I

CORE

ACTIVITIES

ASSOCIATED

WITH

INTELLECTUAL

PROPERTY

EXPLOITATION

and concerns of industry. Such activities include:

- ❖ Staff representation on industrial committees.
- ❖ Attendance at industrial meetings.
- ❖ Undertaking commissioned research.
- ❖ Participating in NERC seminars aimed at commercial audiences.
- ❖ Participating in market research projects.
- ❖ Staff exchanges with industry.

NERC's staff appraisal systems should include the need for staff to undertake activities that result in technology transfer and exploitation, of which IP identification is one extremely important element.

The identification of commercially valuable IP within NERC on a continual basis is a crucially important step in generating more exploitation activity from its research. The experience of best developed practice in this critical area should be shared regularly and frequently between all staff. Formalising this process should be considered by management.

Intellectual Property Ownership

IP Ownership and Rights of Use

Owning IP is, in principle, no different from owning any other kind of property: ownership may be transferred, sold or assigned. Any Institute or Council can assign its IP ownership to another organisation for a fee or royalty payment, from the future exploitation of the IP; however, it must be recognised that in this case long term control is in the hands of a third party.

If IP ownership is retained by NERC, permission can be given to a third party to exploit. This is usually done by licensing the rights to make, have made, use or sell a product. Income is then generated from fees and associated royalty payments derived from successful commercialisation by the third party.

Determining Ownership

In principle, the creator or the inventor is the rightful initial owner of IP, but this is subject to the terms of any contract between the creator/inventor and the employer. Additionally any other existing contractual relationship can define the ownership of the arising IP. For example, where an individual has been specifically contracted to write a piece of software for a financial consideration, the provider of the finance can claim legal title.

It is important that in advance of any work for a third party that the ownership of any ensuing IP is clearly established. Commercially, however, the real issue is the right of access to exploit IP under the terms of a specific contractual arrangement between the relevant parties, ie, owner and potential exploiter.

Externally Funded Research: NERC as Contractor

NERC recognises that those who pay for research undertaken by NERC have a claim to certain ownership and exploitation rights associated with the results of the work. When negotiating the terms of the contract NERC will normally agree that intellectual property rights associated with any invention, design, information, report or other work arising out of the performance of the contracted work will be the property of the organisation commissioning the work. Such an arrangement might be **CONDITIONAL** on the following:

- ❖ That the organisation grants to NERC a royalty-free, non-exclusive right to use the invention, know-how or other IP that results from the work for the sole purpose of academic research (although it is generally recognised that research activities without any commercial exploitation intention do not require a licence).
- ❖ That the organisation grants to NERC the right to publish the results of the work. Where the organisation expects the results to have commercial value, either a limited period of confidentiality before publication shall be negotiated or publication may only occur with the company's prior agreement, which agreement shall not be unreasonably withheld.
- ❖ That if NERC wishes to commercially exploit any IP resulting from the work, NERC will make a formal written request to the company. The company shall respond to such a request within sixty days, and will consider granting NERC a royalty bearing licence on a case-by-case basis.
- ❖ In circumstances where NERC contributes

background research to the work, NERC will wish to retain or share the exploitation rights to the results of the foreground work.

- ❖ **Divided or shared ownership of IP is not to be recommended:** single ownership with arrangements for exploitation rights should be aimed for in all cases. For example:
 - in the case of a data set there would be a long term benefit to many with the retention of the IP within NERC with other complementary datasets and where models for interpretation are updated in line with knowledge development
 - in the case of a patent being obtained the benefit may be to lodge ownership of the IP in the private sector, where there are the resources to police and defend the patents.
- ❖ Where the company is only partially funding the work, NERC will wish to enter into an agreed arrangement for the IP ownership and exploitation rights to the best advantage of Council:
 - if the exploitation rights are for commercial gain the most appropriate place for the exploitation rights lie within the private sector
 - if the exploitation rights are required largely for marketing purposes, for example as the basis of an enquiry service or as a precursor to other consultancy and research, then the rights may lie best with NERC.

NERC as a Research Customer

NERC commissions a considerable amount of research from outside bodies. All Intellectual Property (whether subject to patent, registered design, copyright or other protection) in any invention, design, information, report or

other work arising out of the performance of the contracted work should be the property of NERC. In addition:

- ❖ The contractor shall promptly inform the NERC of any result capable of being patented as a proprietary right which may arise in consequence of the work, and shall, if required by the NERC but at NERC's expense, do all that is necessary to enable the NERC to obtain such patents or other protection for its rights as it may require.
- ❖ NERC reserves the right to use the results of the work and decide that the results shall be publicly disseminated or commercially exploited.
- ❖ Where NERC decides that any IP should be commercially exploited it will consider any offer of licence proposed by the contractor.

The only exception to this policy is for work carried out under a Research Grant by an HEI. Under the terms announced by the Secretary of State for Education and Science in 1985, HEIs are granted ownership of, and exploitation rights for, the results of the work. For further discussion of this policy with respect to datasets please refer to sections 3.2 and 5.2 in the 1996 Data Policy Handbook. However, it would be possible, with the agreement of all parties, in the case of large programmes, where the exploitation is likely to depend upon collective action and where financial returns may be significant, to vest the ownership of the IP from all of the projects within NERC. Any agreement would then need to address the issue of royalty payments back to the contributing HEIs.

Historical Comment

Historically, commercial exploitation of IP was not

considered to be important for NERC. A significant proportion of NERC's IP, in particular its datasets, contain the results of research undertaken for external organisations many years ago. Little information is available about the agreed IP ownership conditions made at the time of the research, which hampers the process of securing benefits to the scientific community from its use.

NERC's ability to commercially exploit this IP is hindered by a lack of clarity on the associated ownership and exploitation rights. It is clear from this that in the past NERC has entered into research contracts without consideration being given to securing IP ownership or licences. Furthermore, it has also become involved with third parties without the security of any prior contractual agreement. As a result, a legacy of IP with doubtful rights of ownership and agreements for use has been inherited. Much work will be required to resolve these issues.

Setting Up Contracts

Contracts for each research project undertaken on behalf of a third party must be approved by NERC's Procurement and Commercial Section which ensures that an appropriate IP ownership position has been negotiated with each party depending on the circumstances of each contract.

Research project leaders should liaise closely with NERC's Procurement and Commercial Section prior to entering into any negotiations with external organisations. In this way NERC will be able to secure the most beneficial IP ownership position possible.

Valuation of Intellectual Property

The valuation of IP is primarily dependent upon having a buyer, however it is useful to have some feel for the value of your IP prior to entering any negotiations. This handbook cannot provide a definitive guide to IP valuation but it can give an idea of the important principles. More detail can be obtained from whole books devoted to the subject¹.

Assigning a value to your IP is difficult and will necessarily involve some knowledge of the potential market. The following points should be borne in mind when arriving at and declaring the price that you want to sell at and comparing this price with the price you are offered:

- ❖ The market must need it.
- ❖ The amount of work required to transfer the technology to the market will affect the value.
- ❖ The degree of risk will affect the price.
- ❖ Will the product be entering a new market?
- ❖ Is this a new area for the company you are talking to?
- ❖ Do you have experience of dealing with commercial companies?
- ❖ You need to judge the benefit to your buyer's business.
- ❖ Historical costs are not relevant to the price of the IP, but they may be useful during negotiations.

You should develop a feel for the value of your IP for specific uses before you seek a commercial partner as this will provide a starting point for discussions and negotiations.

Valuing New IP

Appropriate choices for exploitation can only be made with clear quantitative information on the market potential of the IP in question. Valuation is an essential component of the IP management process.

As well as direct financial returns, indirect benefits, such as increased consultancy work, sales and commissioned research can arise from the dissemination of IP, for example, in the form of know-how. These also contribute to the value of any particular piece of IP.

Estimating Value

The market is the starting point for assessing the commercial value of any IP. No matter how technologically refined or intellectually beguiling a piece of IP might be, it will not be exploitable if there is no market. Market information will provide insight into what could be charged for any new product or service offered and the expected level of sales. Use the market information checklist in Appendix 3 to assist you.

The potential value to NERC from the commercial exploitation of new IP can be crudely estimated by subtracting the exploitation costs from the arising commercial revenue. Dialogue with potential end-users is required to make realistic estimates of exploitation costs and revenues. Indeed such a dialogue is essential so that any internally generated NERC estimates of these figures can be validated.

The sourcing of relevant market information is a time consuming task, but it is often possible to collect some initial, albeit crude, data by referring to a number of

¹ *Valuation of Intellectual Property and Intangible Assets* by Gordon V Smith and Russel L Pau. 2nd Ed. published by Wiley and Sons 1995.

sources detailed in Information Sources on page 42.

Assistance in the valuation of IP should be sought initially through local contacts and then through NERC's Technology Interaction Group. Discussions should be held at as early a stage as possible in the valuation process.

Aspects that should be discussed include:

- ❖ Reference to commercial literature, directories, prior market research reports, etc.
- ❖ Introduction to relevant commercial contacts.
- ❖ Undertaking or arranging an in-depth market investigation.

Ultimately, IP only has a value if you can find a buyer who is willing to pay the price that you have arrived at. If you wish to transfer the exploitation activity to outside NERC then you will need to either:

- ❖ take it yourself
- ❖ find an exploitation partner
- ❖ sell your IP through a technology offer which can be placed with one of a number of specialist companies.

Enhancing Value

Field validation trials and relevant methods of certification can significantly improve the value of IP and may be worth investing in prior to finding an exploitation partner.

Intellectual Property as a Marketing Tool

Using identified IP as the basis of a product or service, appreciated by the market as being scientifically or technologically excellent, can have a very positive impact on the reputation of those behind its development.

Confirmation of this point has been demonstrated by the

many universities who have found that exploiting their IP has had the unexpected benefit of increasing the amount of research being commissioned by industry. Those universities have demonstrated clearly that they can operate professionally and produce excellent research of relevance to industry; the result of this is that further research is commissioned by industry at these universities.

EC legislation dictates that environmental data should be freely available. This does not mean that it should be given away free of charge, but that associated costs should be reasonable and should not limit the availability of the data. Selling IP at a discounted price, in the interests of marketing, is in some cases beneficial, however it can destroy the market place for future products.

Legal Protection of IP

Intellectual property can be protected through a range of legal procedures. These can include patents, copyright, design rights, trademarks and confidential information. Choosing the appropriate protection procedure (Table 1) depends on the nature of the intellectual property as well as the extent to which exploitation of the IP is being sought and the scale of the expected financial return.

The proper protection of IP may make the difference between commercial success and failure.

In addition to protecting your own rights, the actions involved in protecting IP may also avoid the infringement of the rights of others which may be uncovered by prior searches.

Copyright

Copyright gives rights to the creator of the work. The rights deal with the copying, adapting and issuing to the public and broadcasting the copyright material. In many cases, authors will also have the right (specified in the UK

Table 1. Forms of IP and appropriate protection.

	Trademarks	Copyright	Design Rights	Registered Design	Patents	Confidential Information
Words on paper	✓	✓				✓
Company name	✓					
Product name						
Pictorial design logo	✓	✓				
Technical drawing		✓	✓	✓		✓
Mechanical device			✓	✓	✓	
Electrical device			✓		✓	
Computer program		✓			✓	✓
Test method					✓	✓
Manufacturing method					✓	✓
Chemical process					✓	✓
Chemical compound					✓	✓
Datasets		✓				✓
Maps		✓				
Methodology						✓

1988 Patent Act as a Moral Right) to be cited as the creator of the work. Copyright now exists for 70 years after the death of the author as the result of an amendment to the 1988 Act which came into effect on 1 January 1996, although Crown Copyright still only exists for 50 years. In principle, a copyright holder may be able to make legal objection to distortions and mutilations of the work.

Copyright is intended to protect against others copying and exploiting the form in which a copyright work exists. Although in some cases it can be difficult to distinguish the form from the idea, copyright is not intended to and does not protect ideas.

Copyright is automatic. The moment an original piece of work is created it is subjected to copyright. There are no formal registration procedures required, nevertheless it is advisable to consider proving copyright by the following procedure: a copy of the complete work should be signed by all authors, dated and posted to yourself using registered post and should remain in the sealed, franked, unopened envelope. The envelope should be lodged in a safe deposit at a bank or with your legal advisor.

Copyright Subject Matter

Copyright protects a wide range of subject-matter; the most common examples include literary works, visual forms, records and audio recordings. Copyright does not exist in a name or a title (consideration may have to be given to possible filing for trademark protection when a "name" is considered to be commercially important). For NERC, copyright protection is commercially significant for databases, maps, survey reports etc., and is particularly relevant for computer software.

Copyright provides the legal protection necessary

for the exploitation of NERC's electronic databases which represent one of NERC's most valuable intellectual property assets. With the increased use of electronic media, such as CD-ROM, on-line services (both Internet and satellite systems) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS), NERC's electronic databases are acquiring significant long term commercial potential.

An EC directive for the copyright protection of electronic databases has been drafted, but has not yet been adopted. The latest version, at the time of going to press, is available in the Official Journal Series C(1995)288 published on 30/10/95. It aims to protect databases in two ways:

- ❖ The first relates to the originality of the database. A database represents the author's own intellectual creation by reason of the selection or arrangement of its contents.
- ❖ The second is concerned with the contents, rather than the structure or form, of the database. This can prevent the unauthorised extraction or re-use of the contents of the database for commercial purposes. However, insubstantial parts of a database can be extracted and used for commercial purposes as long as the original source is acknowledged. The definition of "insubstantial" is still to be tested before a court of law.

Data should only be released under licence, so that NERC can maintain control over the way the customer uses the data. NERC retains the copyright of data licensed to customers and thus precludes them from passing the data on to third parties without permission and/or receipt of an appropriate consideration to NERC.

NERC produces a wide range of maps including

land cover, vegetation, gravity, magnetic, oceanographic, wave, current, geological and hydrological which are all protected by copyright. In order for NERC's maps to acquire copyright protection two basic conditions must be fulfilled:

- ❖ The work must have been given a certain form as copyright only applies to the expression of an idea.
- ❖ The work must have a degree of originality; a map is essentially the author's depiction of reality and by its nature is an original piece of work.

Computer programs are protected on the same basis as literary works. Conversion of a program into or between computer languages and codes corresponds to 'adapting' a work and storing any work in a computer amounts to 'copying' the work. The running of a computer program or displaying work on a VDU will usually involve copying and thus require the consent of the copyright holder.

NERC has developed a substantial amount of copyrighted computer software, for example:

HYDATA
 Micro-FSR
 HYRROM
 ECoS
 Micro Low Flow
 UKDMAP
 POLPRED
 GRAVMAG

Enforcing Copyrights

NERC is intent on enforcing copyright compliance as outlined in its software licences. Copyright infringement,

resulting from the illegal copying of programs, can be monitored or controlled through the use of:

- ❖ Electronic hard keys (colloquially referred to as a dongle): a security device which plugs into a PC and allows operation of the protected software.
- ❖ Copy protection programs which are written into the software package to prohibit multiple copying.

Patents

Rights Provided by Patents

A patent is a monopoly right to exclude others from using an invention without the owner's permission. The owner thus has the right to take legal action to prevent others from exploiting commercially the subject matter of the patent.

A UK patent lasts for a maximum period of 20 years dating from the application filing date. A UK patent confers protection only within the UK and the Isle of Man. International patent protection is available to cover further countries.

The grant of a patent for an invention is not an indication that it has any commercial value but it may be the source for its value.

Patentable Inventions

Patents are intended to protect useful inventions, whether they are products or processes. In the UK, for inventions to be patentable they must be:

- ❖ novel
- ❖ involve an inventive step and
- ❖ be susceptible to industrial application.

NOVEL: the invention must not have been made public in any way, anywhere in the world, before the date on

which an application for a patent is filed.

INVENTIVE STEP: it must be obvious to someone with a good knowledge and experience of the subject that it represents an inventive step when compared with what is already known.

INDUSTRIAL APPLICATION: the invention must be capable of being made or used in an industrial sector.

The following do not constitute patentable inventions:

- ❖ The discovery of a previously unknown natural phenomenon.
- ❖ A new theory to account for observed phenomena.
- ❖ A new mathematical procedure.
- ❖ A new method for presenting information.
- ❖ An idea.
- ❖ Intellectual or aesthetic activities eg, written text or painted pictures.

It should be recognised that computer programs as such are not patentable, but original apparatus or methods incorporating computer programs may be patentable.

Patentability of Biological Material

Living material can be patented and is treated no differently from other patentable inventions. Proteins, genes, vectors and transgenic organisms are patentable if they are isolated and have a defined use (eg recombinant technology).

Why Patent?

Manufacturers or potential financiers are more likely to invest in the development of a new product or process which is the subject of a patent application or a granted patent when they can see good prospects for recovery of

their investment from future revenues.

- ❖ Patents or patent applications may be of particular value when seeking external contracts as they can provide evidence of credibility or commercial potential.
- ❖ Once filed, patents will aid the dissemination of NERC's scientific achievements because they are documents of public record available to all.

The Cost of Filing a Patent

The likely commercial returns from a patented invention must be balanced against the cost of obtaining, maintaining and possibly defending a patent. A patent application to be filed in the UK initially is relatively cheap with a cost of between £500-£1000 although in complex cases this may rise to £3000; most of this finance is taken up with agent fees. Costs will rise both at the completion phase and for any further geographical coverage which is sought (costs of £5,000-£10,000 should be budgeted, although wide geographic coverage could raise the costs to £50,000).

Issues such as the rate of technological development in the patented field as well as the size and growth rate of the relevant market sectors must be considered if patent application is envisaged.

The legal costs involved in defending a patent as a result of possible infringements or counterclaims can be significant, particularly in the United States. If decisions on these matters are foreseen they should be referred to senior management before any costs are incurred. In addition, legal advice should be sought from the Procurement and Contracts Section before ANY communication is made with a possible infringer.

Good Practice

Good practice within NERC should be based on a combination of IP identification procedures with the appropriate assessment of the commercial potential of any particular item of IP.

It is important to ensure that your laboratory notebook is maintained in a clean, tidy and well ordered manner and that it is regularly signed and witnessed, perchance you file a patent in the USA. A recent change in US law has meant that the "first to invent principle" is now also applicable to inventors outside the USA; the rest of the world follows the "first to file" principle. The British Technology Group (BTG plc) produces a short guide on good laboratory notebook practice which can be obtained free of charge from BTG plc, the address can be found in the information section of this handbook.

Cautions

Public disclosure of an invention prior to filing a patent application must be avoided. There are many ways in which public disclosure can occur, for example:

- ❖ Publication of an article or paper in a magazine or journal prior to the filing date.
- ❖ By circulating abstracts or drafts of papers in advance of application.
- ❖ By word of mouth: making a speech or presentation, or even just talking informally to a group containing members of the public, such as institute visitors. Particular care should be taken with the content of conference poster sessions.
- ❖ By careless use of e-mail.
- ❖ Question-and-answer sessions at open conferences should be treated with caution; information judiciously concealed during a carefully prepared

speech or presentation can easily slip out in spontaneous response to an unexpected question.

- ❖ Offering a product, embodying the invention, for sale prior to filing.

Obtaining a Patent

To secure UK patent rights a written application must be made to the Patent Office. This document consists of a complete specification which describes the invention, using drawings as appropriate, and a set of claims which define the monopoly being sought. **A patent specification is a complex legal document and its drafting should be undertaken by a qualified and experienced professional such as a patent agent or specialist legal attorney.**

The patent must be held in the name of the Natural Environment Research Council as this is the only legal entity of NERC, however it is possible to include sub divisions of the organisation.

In many circumstances there are overseas markets for new inventions; it may be necessary to secure a separate patent for each country being targeted although this is not always so: it is possible to secure a pan-European patent from the European Patent Office. Since patenting is a complex matter staff are referred in the first instance to the chapter in these notes on support and training. If the international dimension is significant then discussions should be held with TIG personnel prior to any decision on incurring legal costs.

The patenting cycle is illustrated in the form of a worksheet which is included in Appendix 2 of this handbook. After first filing a number of decisions have to be made about the geographic coverage. Your Patent Agent will advise you about the best course of action for your individual case.

Confidential Information

Keeping information secret or confidential can be an effective strategy for protecting “know-how” and “show-how”. Know-how is a term often associated with technical information such as drawings, manuals, specifications and designs. Show-how is used to describe specific technical skills possessed by certain individuals which may be necessary to implement an invention. Confidential information can also comprise commercial intelligence (eg market research), commercial strategies (eg customer lists, pricing strategies etc), and methodologies (eg how to design and undertake a research project).

Unlike copyright, confidential information does not need to be reduced to any particular form in order for it to be protected. It can often be used in conjunction with other forms of intellectual property rights; for example, an engineering drawing can be both confidential and protected by copyright.

NERC is continuously developing scientific methods and related procedures. Maintaining control over these can be extremely difficult as there are many ways for these forms of IP to become known and used by others, including through:

- ❖ *The outline of research methodologies in contract submissions.* These may be appropriated by non-NERC personnel having sight of the document and represent a potential loss of income.
- ❖ *Ex-employees of NERC who take valuable information with them,* the use of which can lead to competition.
- ❖ *Visitors to NERC sites who become privy to key information* (without having signed a non-disclosure agreement) which they take away and may use in competitive initiatives.

The law provides a range of useful defensive actions for ensuring that valuable information is kept confidential by those who have become privy to it. These actions include:

- ❖ breach of contractual obligations not to misuse or disclose information
- ❖ breach of trust
- ❖ breach of confidence.

These may still apply even after termination of a contract such as employment.

In order to secure legal protection against others making use of information valuable to NERC it is necessary that:

- ❖ the information is not publicly known and
- ❖ recipients of the information must become subject to an obligation to keep it confidential.

The obligation to keep information confidential does not necessarily need to be contractual, as the obligation can be implied. An implied duty of confidence results if the circumstances are such that any reasonable person, in the place of the recipient of the information, would have realised that the information was given to them in confidence. An obligation to keep information confidential entails not disclosing or using the information without permission of the person to whom the obligation is owed.

This obligation can be made more explicit by having the recipient sign a confidentiality agreement in advance of any disclosure. It is good practice to label all important documents with *Commercial in Confidence* or similar. Any actions which help the reasonable person to become more aware of the commercial sensitivity of the information being disclosed reinforces their obligation to

treat it as confidential. This is good practice which should be followed when drafting contract proposals.

Problems with Confidential Information

The use of confidential information as a means of protecting commercially valuable IP over long periods can be difficult for scientists to accept because they expect to be able to disseminate and exchange their ideas and research findings freely. This particular IP protection tactic is best employed when the commercial opportunity in question is of a limited life span.

Confidentiality can be lost at any time as a result of a public disclosure by another source, eg somebody who has independently conceived the same invention.

Deliberate or inadvertent disclosure is ever present when commercially valuable IP is protected solely through the use of confidential information especially when the commercial opportunity is large or lucrative.

Advantages with Confidential Information

Confidential information as a means of protecting IP has the advantage of low cost associated with its management. There are no formal protection costs unlike those incurred in filing a patent.

Confidential information is an effective protection mechanism when a business is developing rapidly, so that a certain piece of knowledge is quickly superseded by further development. Commercially valuable IP would then only need to be kept confidential over relatively short periods of time.

Trademarks

Trademarks (including service marks) are names or symbols used to identify and distinguish goods or services

from a particular organisation from other similar offerings from other organisations. The commercial value and importance of trademarks are that they:

- ❖ Represent the image and reputation of a company or business.
- ❖ Act as a brand to give a common identity or image to ranges of different kinds of goods and services that have particular characteristics.
- ❖ Give an identity to particular products and services.

Trademark Protection

Trademarks are protected by non-statutory and statutory means:

Non-statutory is a form of common law protection. This form of protection is reactive. Circumstances can arise in which damage is done to NERC through others using marks in businesses similar to NERC's as they result in confusion or misrepresentation; such damaging action by third parties may be restrained. Common law protects us from forms of unfair trading which are known as "passing off". The following conditions must be fulfilled if common law protection is to be used, these are: misrepresentation made by a trader in the course of trade to prospective customers or ultimate consumers of the goods or services supplied which is calculated to injure the business or goodwill of another trader (in the sense that this is a reasonable foreseeable consequence), and which causes actual damage to a business or goodwill of the trader by whom the action is brought.

Statutory protection through registration is also available. The Trade Mark Act of November 1994 should be referred to for further detail as it represents a major change in UK

legal practice. Trade Marks can be registered with the Trade Mark Registry. This form of protection is proactive. Trade Mark registration gives to the holder the right to stop other people using the mark in circumstances which could give rise to confusion or deception and which could be damaging. There are 42 classes of trademark; the help of a qualified agent should be sought, rather than to *do it yourself*, to help to assess which classes it would be prudent for you to consider searching and using for protection. Contact TIG at Swindon for the name of an agent which NERC has used before, as special rates might apply.

NERC Experience

One institute has reviewed the necessity for registering their primary trademark (institute name and logo). This review was stimulated by the discovery that a new consultancy, located nearby, had begun trading under a similar name with the same acronym. The review concluded that Trade Mark protection provided through common law was sufficient to protect its name and logo and that registration was not required. The new consultancy was informed that their choice of name was considered as being damaging to the institute. The consultancy company changed its name and the situation was resolved amicably.

The case for registration of product names and logos as trademarks is probably stronger. In order to establish wide recognition amongst customers of a new product name a clear identity should be created. It will then be easier to prove infringement if others

subsequently use an identical or similar mark.

Situations can also occur where different businesses concurrently develop separate competing products with similar names or logos. Registration of the trademark can ensure absolute priority for its use. Several of NERC's Institutes have registered trademarks for their products.

The British Geological Survey has a registered trademark, WELLOG, which is the trade name of a specific set of equipment and associated software with practical uses within the oil industry. This well logging system is useful for estimating the nature and amount of recoverable hydrocarbons along the length of a test well. After the name's trademark registration, BGS became aware of a similar product marketed using the same name. The situation was resolved amicably.

The Institute of Hydrology has a registered trademark for their Water Information System (WIS). WIS is an integrated system of computer hardware, software and supporting services useful for handling the technical and scientific information requirements of the Water Industry. The system is currently being made available to the market.

Design Rights

Design rights are automatic, the moment an article is created it becomes protected. Ownership lies with the person or organisation that commissioned the design.

Design Rights protect the design of any aspect of the configuration or shape (whether internal or external) of an article of novel design. Functionally a design right operates as a copyright for three-dimensional articles. Design rights prohibit others from reproducing or manufacturing the article for 15 years after its creation. The owner can prevent others from producing working

copies of the article even from technical drawings by exercising their right.

It is possible to register Design Rights at the Designs Registry for added protection. A design can be registered if it has visual appeal and is novel. In order that the novelty criteria is fulfilled the design must not have been disclosed to the public prior to an application for registration being filed. Design Rights and design registration are not mutually exclusive, legal advice should be sought for advice on whether registration is worth applying for. Design registration costs £60 for a single article and £90 for a set. A filing application number is issued within seven days of receipt of the application; it can take up to nine months to receive confirmation that the article has been registered. Registration lasts for five years after which it can be renewed up to a total of 15 years. Legal fees will differ according to the complexity of individual cases.

Exploitation

The delivery of understanding, knowledge and expertise to the NERC user communities such that wealth can be created and conserved as well as the quality of life improved is part of NERC's mission and strategy. In order to achieve this it is essential that NERC undertakes appropriate action to ensure that innovative products and services, based on NERC science, are made available to society and the industrial community. NERC also expects to generate, where appropriate, financial returns from undertaking these actions.

In order to exploit Intellectual Property it is necessary to own the right to exploit, referred to as the Intellectual Property Right (IPR); this is determined in a number of ways. The creator of the IP will own the exploitation right unless that right has been licensed or assigned (ie given or sold) to a second party. The creator of the IP will be bound by any contracts existing before, or drawn up after, the creation of the IP. Retrospective determination of IPR is careless and unsatisfactory and should be avoided.

Increasing awareness of NERC among its current and potential user communities is an important task. It is equally important to increase the awareness throughout NERC of the user community's needs and requirements as a basis for exploiting NERC IP. Additionally, this can highlight technological modifications or advancements that could be made to products to ensure that they continue to meet users' evolving needs. In turn this may require further research.

The marketing of products and/or services provides a useful medium through which communication between NERC staff and industry can occur and new partnerships stimulated.

Exploitation Routes

NERC can secure direct financial benefits from exploiting its IP through a number of routes:

- ❖ Internal - means developing and marketing the products, eg software in house.
- ❖ External - licensing the exploitation rights (IPR) to other organisations. It is also possible to assign the exploitation rights although the implications of this must be considered carefully.
- ❖ Partnership - entering into commercial partnerships.

Internal Exploitation

In the majority of cases the manufacture, sales and distribution of products is best conducted in the private sector which has the infrastructure to provide customer support and servicing. When scientifically complex technologies, such as the type developed within NERC, are to be exploited further support may be required from the staff who developed the IP; for example, external users of NERC's computer programs often require scientific support, or customisation, that can only be provided by NERC scientists.

In some cases NERC services or products are used as a marketing tool to stimulate higher value consultancy or to generate new research contracts, in these instances the exploitation is most preferably handled through an internal mechanism which may need to be set up specifically.

Although one awareness and image building mechanism, that has been used by NERC, is the provision of inexpensive products that demonstrate the breadth of research and quality of intellectual effort resident in NERC,

down-pricing is not encouraged as it may destroy the market place for future exploitation activities. The commonly adopted practice among industry to achieve this kind of exposure is the creation of demonstration packages, brochures and other marketing functions.

Examples of where NERC's Centres and Surveys have successfully set up structures to facilitate exploitation generally apply to the following type of products:

- ◆ **Specialised software with low volume of sales:** The Institute of Hydrology set up a Software Group to develop, market and support computer software programs developed at the Institute. In order to market these computer programs the Software Group produces promotional literature and newsletters, conducts targeted mail-shots and organises software open days.
- ◆ **Advice/Data:** The Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory has established the *POL Applications Group*, through which industry is encouraged to access advice, data, statistics and modelling software developed at the Institute.
- ◆ **Data:** Computerised data centres have been established at NERC sites to provide information and advisory services for a wide range of users from the scientific community, industry, local and national government and overseas agencies. Concentrating data holdings and providing a common gateway through which information about NERC's data holdings can be obtained is intended to assist NERC publicise and market its data holdings.
- ◆ **Specialised/customised maps:** BGS directly controls the retailing of a range of printed maps

produced at its Institutes. Published maps are predominately sold by mail order and at BGS Institute site offices. The HMSO and the Ordnance Survey also participate in the retailing of BGS maps.

Exploitation by Others

Another route for realising direct financial benefits from NERC's IP is to assign ownership or to licence IP exploitation rights to another party in exchange for a financial payment.

An external organisation usually has access to key resources, such as manufacturing, dedicated staff resource, trained sales force and customer support capabilities, that NERC Institutes cannot support. Additionally, they may have a better understanding of the market place and use a well developed and appropriate distribution network. Because of this they are often better placed to realize the full commercial potential of a given piece of NERC's IP.

Assignment of IP

Assignment of IP ownership has certain advantages over licensing, such as transferring the obligation to defend against infringers. However, NERC has been reluctant to assign ownership of its IP to another organisation because NERC will consequently lose control of the IP. NERC is interested in seeing that the IP it develops is put to proper use and that the benefits to society are maximised. Through assignment, NERC may not be able to measure the extent to which its IP is being used.

Licensing IP

The alternative to assignment of ownership is to licence IP exploitation rights. The main advantages of licensing from NERC's perspective are:

- ❖ Non-exclusive licences provide the opportunity to licence exploitation rights to a number of organisations, potentially maximising the use of the IP.
- ❖ Non-performance clauses can be included to prevent organisations blocking IP exploitation.
- ❖ Royalty payments provide an effective mechanism for measuring the level of success of the exploitation.

Licensing exploitation rights is most effective when there is little need for subsequent technical involvement from the research organisation, ie, when a standardised product can be developed and when the intellectual property can be readily reduced to a negotiable form protected either through patenting or copyright.

Locating Licencees

Finding licencees is time-consuming and can be expensive, and negotiating a licence agreement even more so; these tasks require considerable experience and a wide range of contacts. However, there are numerous brokerage services available for finding potential licencees (see Partners for Exploitation, page 45). Additionally, some of NERC's larger funders of research offer assistance in locating licencees for IP generated during research funded by them. For example MAFF's IP Liaison Unit will work closely with NERC scientists to ensure commercial exploitation of MAFF funded research.

Research Partnerships

The formation of partnerships for research can remove the problem of finding a licensee as the industrial partner will normally licence the generated IP and do the exploitation

themselves. Often this is the incentive for their participation in the collaboration and it may be written into the research contract that they have first refusal to the exploitation rights. **It is imperative in these circumstances that the ownership of any IP is:**

- ❖ Whenever possible retained by NERC (except patents).
- ❖ Agreed before any work is started in order that the resulting exploitation rights can be licensed successfully.

Sale of Know-how

A complement or alternative to licensing may be the sale of proprietary know-how. Know-how is not reducible to a simple negotiable form (such as a patent), and its transfer to a buyer is likely to involve considerable effort on the part of the vendor: procedures need to be written down in a manual, training provided, and assistance made available during commissioning. In most cases, however, the cash expenditure is negligible compared to patenting and licensing, and the opportunity cost is unlikely to be much higher. This approach may be appropriate in cases where patent protection for the invention is likely to be weak, and/or where the market prospects are judged to be insufficient to warrant patenting costs.

Joint Ventures

Joint Ventures are an effective way of overcoming the problems associated with licensing and the sale of know-how. They allow those who understand the IP in question to work closely with those who have commercial expertise and provide a vehicle for two organisations to pool their strengths. The Joint Venture approach has the added advantage of spreading the commercial risk

exposure over more than one organisation.

The creation of a Joint Venture company can help facilitate the acquisition of venture capital or even act as a prelude to the company being sold.

The Joint Venture approach is particularly appropriate in situations where an R&D establishment is expected to make a succession of exploitable innovations. This may be expected in areas of technology that happen to be in rapid advance such as telecommunications, computer science, or the biotechnologies.

NERC has been active in undertaking joint-ventures with industrial partners to develop and exploit opportunities based on NERC's IP, some examples of successful joint ventures are:

- ❖ PML, in partnership with Shell Ventures UK Limited, undertook to develop and market a PC-based simulator of contaminants in estuarine environments. The ECoS program has been marketed to environmental managers and consultants.
- ❖ The Institute of Hydrology entered into a marketing joint venture with Hydraulics Research. The intention of creating this joint venture company (Wallingford Water) was to capitalise on the breadth of IP resident in these two organisations.

Exploitation Company

In certain cases it may be appropriate to establish a commercial enterprise wholly under the control of NERC for the purposes of exploiting certain intellectual properties. Such an approach would be relevant when continued close liaison with the researchers is essential for

success, such as when either the manufacturing process or the product support requires a continuing and high level of technical support.

The establishment of a wholly owned subsidiary could provide the framework for moving the exploitation activity away from NERC. The arms length, business relation with NERC would allow the exploitation company to secure external venture capital or government grants for small businesses as needed. Ultimately, the enterprise might be sold to external interests.

Creation of a separate operating entity through which to exploit a given IP (or set of IPs) would allow managerial and operational flexibility; for example, the commercial enterprise would be free from systems and procedures appropriate for a research organisation but inappropriate for a commercial initiative.

NERC Small Business Scheme

The NERC operates a Small Business Scheme under which its employees have special terms of employment over two years to allow them to form independent businesses to market specific technologies and/or services. During this time there must be no business relationship between NERC and the new business. This scheme provides a "safety blanket" for scientists who have the know-how, the drive and the enthusiasm for transferring their technology into a viable product or service.

Finding an Exploitation Partner Through Collaborative Work

The location of a suitable partner to assist with exploitation activities can be complex and time consuming. In some cases, such as instances of collaborative research, or areas where there is a long

standing history of contract work, the partner may be an obvious choice. Developing a relationship with relevant industrial sectors, through a variety of ways, can be the beginning of your search.

Through a Partnership Scheme

Participation in partnership initiatives such as the LINK programme, Teaching Company Scheme, Foresight Challenge fund bids and attending industrial conferences and exhibitions can help to develop a trusting relationship with the private sector. Other ways of locating a partner are through technology brokerages.

Through a Brokerage Network

Finding a partner through a network requires you to write a technology offer to post on the network. A technology offer describes a piece of Intellectual Property which is available for sale or licensing. The offer is distributed through one of a variety of networks (some of which are described on page 46) in a newsletter or as a CD-ROM.

A technology offer is a short document which would be difficult for the researchers closely involved with the work to write well. The document must be clear, concise and free from jargon and written so that the target audience easily grasp the principles; it is often best written by someone not too close to the work. The opportunity that is presented by the offered IP needs to be clearly stated. Essentially the offer must state:

- ❖ What the IP could be used for.
- ❖ What it does/achieves.
- ❖ Why someone else would want it.
- ❖ The current state of development.

Companies and individuals interested in taking a piece of IP forward to product development will respond to the offer directly.

Help and guidance in writing a technology offer is available from your local Intellectual Property/Marketing Officer and also from Technology Interaction in Swindon.

Summary

Different exploitation routes are relevant to different types of intellectual property, markets and purposes. It is therefore important for active involvement and understanding, at all levels throughout NERC, in the process of *identification* and *valuation* of IP and in consideration of potential *exploitation* routes. Some exploitation routes may require a funding mechanism to assist with the different stages of exploitation (Finance for Exploitation is described on page 50). The main criterion is to locate an exploitation partner.

Whilst there are reasons for using the internal mechanism it should be recognised that in many cases the external exploitation route would have greater benefit, not least because the relevant expertise is not widely available within NERC, but also because the profile of NERC throughout industry would be raised.

NERC's IP can provide indirect benefits to Council: in addition to the revenues generated through its consultancy activities, business ventures and increased interaction with industry, it will raise the public profile of NERC. This increased awareness of NERC's capabilities and skills to deliver new technologies to user communities is likely to be a further stimulus in generating new research contracts.

PART 2

EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF EXPLOITATION

Stimulation of Exploitation into a New Environment

Introduction

The implementation of a new or modified practice, such as the exploitation of Intellectual Property, within an organisation may require the modification of the existing reward schemes. In order to assess whether a reward scheme should be modified it is important to assess what rewards are available and how they can be modified or enhanced to be applied to the desired practice.

The purpose of the NERC reward scheme is to encourage individual behaviour consistent with the overall mission of the organisation which in its shortest form for NERC is "excellence and relevance" for each individual.

A successful reward scheme delivers:

- ❖ Management coordinated aims and objectives.
- ❖ A balance of short term and long term effects.

Any reward scheme must be continually monitored to evaluate its impact and to address any problems that arise.

Motivational Factors

The principle aim in motivating employees is to create a situation where the driving force for desired action comes from within the individual. Many professionals, including scientists, are internally motivated by the quest for new knowledge, excellence and self development, but this may not encompass the interests and aims of the corporate body such as relevance to users. Motivational factors of any job can be considered in the terms of two general categories, intrinsic and extrinsic motivators.

Extrinsic motivation is provided by the organisation itself and encompasses financial remuneration and

promotion. Other forms of recognition include office space and factors relating to the status and prestige of the job ie, these rewards are external to the job itself.

Intrinsic motivation comes from the worker and the desire of the worker to do the job; it is inherent within the role of the job and the working environment such as interpersonal relationships. It may also be described as the associated self satisfaction and sense of well-being from working and completing tasks. It is possible to enhance the intrinsic reward by improving the level of self satisfaction, for example by the design of working methods and encouraging employee involvement in decision making processes.

The elements of a job may be subdivided into motivators, which increase motivation:

- ❖ Achievement.
- ❖ Recognition including financial recognition.
- ❖ Work itself.
- ❖ Responsibility.
- ❖ Advancement

and hygiene factors which cause demotivation when absent. It should be stressed that although the absence of these hygiene factors is demotivating their presence does not result in automatic motivation. Job satisfaction can be enriched by improving:

- ❖ Company policy and administration.
- ❖ Supervision.
- ❖ Interpersonal relationships.
- ❖ Working conditions.
- ❖ Status.
- ❖ Security.

Reward Schemes

Reward schemes which seek to raise motivation levels (for specific behaviour patterns) need to use both intrinsic and extrinsic motivators and ensure that short term gain should not be to the detriment of the long term effect. The well documented cautions about reward schemes include:

- ❖ Doing something in return for an extrinsic reward reduces the interest in the task.
- ❖ One extrinsic motivator leads to the expectation of more.
- ❖ Once given an extrinsic motivator cannot be taken away without consequences such as a reduced level of intrinsic motivation.
- ❖ If a reward scheme identifies winners and losers it is probable that there will be more losers and a consequent reduction in team spirit unless compensatory pressures also exist.

Tangible Rewards

Tangible rewards provide financial remuneration in a variety of ways. By breaking the financial reward scheme into its separate elements it is possible to focus motivation towards different but equally desired practices. It is important that the level of reward provided in each scheme is meaningful to the recipient.

Pay Schemes

Pay schemes fundamentally reward individuals for their work. For a successful scheme the pay should match an individual's realistic expectations and should reflect both the level and scope of the job required and the level of relevant experience which the employee brings to the company.

Salary Increases

Salary increases generally have two components: cost of living and performance related. The cost of living element is determined as a salary percentage and usually reflects the current economic situation and the size of the budget for the year. The performance related element is determined by measuring the employee's performance against the individual's job description and objectives for the year.

Bonus Schemes

These reward the outstanding performance of either individuals or teams, are generally determined by local management, and can be used to encourage a change in behaviour. Motivation is provided by linking a particular reward to specific actions and events.

Share Schemes

Many companies which wish to engender a sense of belonging and interest in the company performance encourage staff to purchase share options, usually at preferential prices. Additionally, staff may be further rewarded for long service by the presentation of shares at the end of each complete year of service. The mechanism can be used whenever there is a company within, or controlled by, the organisation.

Profit Related Pay

The majority of employers offer a performance reward to staff in the form of profit related pay which is paid towards the end of the company's financial year as a percentage of salary. The percentage level is determined by the performance of the company over the previous 12 months. This type of reward encourages employees to

have an interest in the short term performance and long term future of the company and helps to stimulate motivation towards meeting the company's budget, for example increasing tolerance towards stringent spending cuts and meeting dispatch deadlines with the aim of achieving the targets for the year end. This type of mechanism can be implemented whenever there are profit, income or contribution targets.

Non-tangible Rewards

Non-tangible rewards, such as praise, should aim to improve the self confidence and attitude of the recipient and hence improve the working environment. They are usually given by line management and often in direct response to a specific action. Non-tangible rewards complement the tangible element of a reward scheme.

Application of Reward Mechanisms to Exploitation

Introducing exploitation into an environment without such a history will not encourage interest and activity in this area if there is no apparent benefit from doing so. Exploitation will then continue to occur despite the system, not because of it.

The application of extrinsic rewards has been shown to be more successful when the reward is similar or related to the task itself, for example, to encourage someone to read, another book should be given as the reward. Extending this argument to exploitation: if we want to encourage exploitation for financial gain then a financial reward would be appropriate.

A number of companies, and Universities, offer employees who successfully develop a new income stream for the company/University a percentage, on a

sliding scale, of the profits. Usually this is applied when the income has been generated by effort which is outside the job description. Where exploitation activity is within the job description, then success should contribute to a raise in salary or promotion. This type of scheme demonstrates to other employees that they too can receive further financial reward if they expand their attitude to their job.

Aims of NERC Reward Schemes in Relation to User Needs (Exploitation)

Within the context of its new mission statement arising from the 1993 Science White Paper, NERC wishes to nurture and promote quality science and bring this to bear upon the needs of its user community. It must work in partnership with user communities to ensure that ideas emerging from the science base contribute to wealth creation and improved quality of life.

Accordingly, NERC must continue to reward excellent science but in the light of the White Paper there is a need to ensure that by being made more relevant to users NERC science is fully and appropriately exploited. There is a requirement to encourage innovation, particularly with respect to novel approaches, to ensure that research outputs are exploited by NERC user communities and so improve UK economic performance and quality of life.

Specifically the above requires:

- ❖ Excellent basic, strategic and applied science.
- ❖ A greater awareness in NERC of user community needs, particularly from industry and commerce as well as improved links with government departments and other public sector organisations.
- ❖ The formation of research partnerships with

users (eg co-funding of science vote programmes through schemes such as LINK).

- ❖ Ensuring that where possible the outcomes of the research are exploited through increased technology and knowledge transfer.
- ❖ Securing worthwhile and profitable income streams for NERC Centre/Surveys through:
 - new opportunities for commissioned research
 - income from licensing and commercialisation of NERC IP
 - promoting income generating opportunities for NERC
 - spin out companies if appropriate.
- ❖ Increased efficiency.
- ❖ Effective leadership and management.
- ❖ Teamwork and cooperation within NERC and with universities and user communities.

Existing Motivation Mechanisms within NERC

There are currently a number of reward schemes available within NERC designed to reward staff appropriately, these include both monetary and non-monetary mechanisms:

- ❖ **Promotion:** within fluid graded posts or using individual merit promotion (IMP) and personal promotion (PP). Promotion rewards individuals for continuing development and reflects the level appropriate for a particular job.
- ❖ **Basic pay.** This rewards individuals for their effort; the level of pay is related to the job description and for existing staff reflects a combination of seniority and post weight and for new entrants it is related to experience and post weight.
- ❖ **Performance Related Pay (PRP)** rewards staff for achieving a satisfactory level of performance as

assessed against a defined set of objectives in a forward job plan. Higher levels of performance pay will be received if the assessment indicates a standard of performance above the level set by the defined objectives. These payments are made once a year and are incremented onto the basic pay; they are judged from the yearly appraisal.

- ❖ **Special Bonus Scheme (SBS):** currently 0.2% of total wages bill. Such bonuses are one off payments which may be made at any time and are typically in the range £500 - £1000. These are normally awarded via line management and are designed to reward high performance; although these have been previously made for efforts outside an individual's job description or for levels of achievement higher than expected it is likely that in the future they will be paid across a wider range of working situations.
- ❖ **Suggestion Scheme:** up to 10% of the annual cost savings through improved efficiency resulting from the suggestion. The reward level varies according to the importance of the suggestion. The intent is to encourage staff to have more involvement with improving common practices within the work environment.
- ❖ **Prizes and Medals:** eg BAS Fuchs Medal and UK Honours provide a means of rewarding individuals at all levels within NERC for an outstanding contribution to NERC. They also serve to raise the public profile of NERC.
- ❖ **NERC Award Scheme.** A scheme has been proposed which reflects the change in the mission statement in response to the 1993 Science White Paper. The awards would be made to individuals or

teams and would probably include a monetary reward, a certificate and perhaps a piece of artwork which would be held for one year. The awards would aim to encourage employees to participate in activities which involve promoting the quality of life, wealth creation through exploitation, and the public understanding of science. There is currently no timetable for the implementation of this.

- ❖ **Personal Development** benefits both the organisation and the individual and can be tailored to different skill levels. Although personal development is not a tangible reward it demonstrates and recognises the interest of NERC, the employer, in the individuals that make up the organisation through:
 - increasing an individual's standing amongst scientific peers through conference contributions, sabbaticals and resources to pursue individual research ideas and time to write and publish scientific papers, articles, books etc.
 - encouraging individuals to gain further qualifications and training in areas relevant to job functions such as NVQs and in non relevant areas such as languages.

Application of Current NERC Motivation Schemes to Exploitation

Currently the NERC motivation and reward mechanisms have been moulded around the promotion of excellence within the NERC community. It is now important to promote relevance as well as excellence. To achieve this the elements contributing to relevance must be specified and included within the description of each scheme.

- ❖ Basic pay is related to the job description, job weight and experience. In order to encourage exploitation through this scheme, job functions related to exploitation, where appropriate, should be included, for example:
 - efforts to secure partnerships, co-funding, communication with users and the engagement of users within the research cycle
 - efforts at exploitation, the development of exploitation partnerships and income generation through licensing.

If these measures are included in the job plan then the performance related pay scheme can also be used to reward efforts directed towards exploitation.

- ❖ Promotion within NERC for *fluid graded scientists* is generally based around publication etc. Promotion criterion should now, when appropriate, embrace both excellence and relevance, in a similar manner to job functions. This will give credit for new skills and experiences developed through exploitation activities which, it is recognised, can assist with the rapid development of strategic, budgetary and planning skills which can be usefully applied across a wide number of other job functions.
- ❖ It is also recognised that *fixed graded scientists* may also be heavily involved in exploitation related activities, as much of the work involved is of an applied nature and, when appropriate, should be rewarded.
- ❖ The Special Bonus Scheme can be used to reward exploitation activities which are not defined within the job description and which may have

resulted through unusual effort. However, the current level of the reward through the Special Bonus Scheme (typically £500 to £1000) may not reflect the effort required for complete exploitation. The limit on rewards from this scheme could perhaps be adjusted.

- ❖ Although training programmes are not always viewed as being an integral part of a traditional reward system they can improve chances of promotion and offer new opportunities. Training programmes could be further developed within NERC which increase the knowledge of staff about: the business environment, accounting, intellectual property, marketing, sales, negotiating and customer expectations and requirements. This would extend the skill base within NERC; staff would gain new skills and intrinsic interest in others would be reinforced. These skills would be applicable to both current NERC business and simultaneously increase the awareness about opportunities for exploitation.

Information Sources

Introduction

Requirements for assistance and guidance on the management of your Intellectual Property will vary according to the stage that you are at and hence the type of information that you need; the advice can also vary in cost. Before seeking advice externally it is important that you build up a clear idea of what your Intellectual Property is. Once you have identified your IP, it may be wise to take heed of a few cautions:

- 1 Be careful how widely you spread your good idea, especially outside NERC. Publishing may jeopardise your exploitation opportunity. Discuss this with your peers or line management.
- 2 Do not prevaricate about investigating the exploitation possibilities. Do it straight away. Draw an outline of what you want to do and what you think you can achieve.
- 3 Do not defer from exploitation because of a lack of resources, this is something which can nearly always be addressed.

Note: the term *product* as used in this chapter refers to the Intellectual Property that is to be exploited and includes technology, products, processes, services, know-how and designs.

This chapter is broadly divided into three sections, described below:

- ❖ Information gathering - why do it?
- ❖ Internal Contacts.
- ❖ External Contacts.

Information Gathering - Market Research

Information gathering about the market for your product is a function which should commence immediately a *product* idea is conceived. The importance of *product* definition and market intelligence cannot be over stressed because the market place of the 1990's is competitive and fast moving. Early market intelligence can help to shape your *product* and integrate customer requirements into the design process to ensure a *product* which is tailored to the customer's needs, desires and future plans.

In addition to early market intelligence it is equally important that the experience of other NERC exploiters and customers are added into your information gathering exercise. Seek to create a feedback loop with interaction and communication between you and your potential customers which will help you to take **intelligent and calculated risks**.

The section on finance for the exploitation process, page 50, describes the marketing process in more detail and how to shape your *product* into a form suitable to approach external sources for finance. In order to gain the confidence and support of industry and financial institutions it is important to present a professional image of ourselves and our *products* by doing a considerable amount of groundwork and initial market research. Additionally refer to Appendix 3, page 64, to identify the information that you will need to collect.

To begin with, answering some simple questions can help to define the nature of your IP and the direction of your information search:

- ❖ What market are you addressing?
- ❖ What is the type of IP ?

- ❖ What protection options are applicable to your IP?
- ❖ What exploitation routes do you have in mind?

By answering these questions you will begin to build a clear picture in your mind of what you want to achieve and provide some focus for further information gathering exercises.

Initially you should look around to see what else is available in the market and try to cover as many of the different angles as possible. Gathering this information is important even if you do not plan to exploit your IP yourself because it will help to develop a feel for the value of your intellectual property and areas in which it might be exploited.

Internal Information Sources

There is a large variation in the level of knowledge and understanding across NERC of exploitation. Some institutions have an employee whose designated responsibility is marketing or Industrial Liaison. Make use of their knowledge, training and experience. Contacts within NERC are listed in Appendix 4. These names represent a network of people within NERC, distributed throughout the Centre/Surveys, who can provide help and guidance on Intellectual Property and exploitation issues and who should always be used as your first point of contact. The contact names will of course be subject to change. Examples of NERC IP are included in Appendix 1.

The process of defining your *product* and finding a suitable exploitation route can be aided by talking to people who have already travelled along the same road.

It is suggested that individuals who need further assistance or when relevant information cannot be found in this guide that they contact NERC Swindon Office

through the Technology Interaction Group (TIG) (Tel: 01793 411764 Fax: 01793 411584). TIG has a large amount of information to hand in addition to a wide range of industrial contacts.

External Contacts

External sources of contact for support, funding, finding partners for exploitation and sources of legal advice both regionally and nationally are covered within this section.

Addresses and telephone numbers were correct at the time of going to press.

Specific or detailed information on IP matters can be obtained from a wide variety of sources. This chapter aims to list some of these sources in addition to a brief description of the main objectives of less well known groups. In addition to looking for advice from these sources it is likely that you will also be looking for funding or for an exploitation partner. There are many ways of finding a partner, either through a specialist technology broker or an industry database obtained from an industry organisation representing a specific sector of industry; a detailed listing of all industry technology associations cannot be covered here, but assistance in locating one is available from TIG.

A source of general information and advice on technology transfer is available through **The European Infrastructure Database - Best Practice** which is published by the European Commission and is a multi-lingual CD-ROM which presents "good practices" distilled from ten years of support to European technology transfer networks by the former SPRINT programme. It is a tool developed by the EC to help Research and Technology Organisations, regional Technology Advisory Centres and technology brokers and other private, public and non-

profit organisations to improve their trans-national innovation support. A copy of this CD-ROM is held by TIG.

For further information or copies contact:

DG X111 D
Dissemination and Exploitation of RTD Results
Technology Transfer and Innovation
Jean Monnet Building
L-2920 Luxembourg
Fax: (352) 43 01 34 544

Innovation/Intellectual Property Specific Societies

Individual membership of a support network for inventors and innovators can be a useful source of information and guidance for the exploitation of IP. Two such bodies are detailed below:

- ❖ **Institute of Patentees and Inventors.** The institute was set up as a first port of call for inventors and it publishes the journal "Future". Membership will give access to advice and guidance on all aspects of inventing and can advise its members on obtaining patent protection. Additionally, meetings are held regularly by groups of regional members. The institute can also help to facilitate contacts for exploitation opportunities through keeping a database of members' inventions.

Institute of Patentees and Inventors
Suite 505a Triumph House
189 Regent Street
London W1R 7WF
Tel: 0171 242 7812

❖ **Intellectual Property Development**

Confederation (IPDC) is a non profit making organisation which offers a wide variety of information and support services and contacts. The confederation's magazine is *Inventors World* and it is published quarterly. For further information contact:

IPDC
72a Bedford Place
Southampton SO15 2DS
Tel: 01703 229112.
Fax: 01703 237854.

- ❖ **Intellectual Property Institute** is a small organisation which holds seminars, has a publication portfolio and a small, but specialist, library in central London.

Charles Clore House
17 Russell Square
London WC1B 5DR
Tel: 0171 637 1721
Fax: 0171 580 4273

- ❖ **Licensing Executives Society** is a non profit making professional and educational society for scientists, engineers, lawyers, marketing executives, academics and anyone else involved in licensing.

Licensing Executives Society
c/o Renate Siebrasse
Batelle Institute
15 Hanover Square
London W1R 9AJ
Tel: 0171 493 0184
Fax: 0171 629 9705

Specialist Legal Firms

There is a large number of legal firms or licensing agents which specialise in the handling of intellectual property, and in some cases specific types of technology. If none of the companies which have previously been employed by NERC are relevant to you then other specialist firms may be contacted either through the local telephone directory or by contacting a professional institution such as:

Chartered Institute of Patent Agents

Staple Inn Buildings
High Holborn
London
WC1V 7PZ
Tel: 0171 405 9450

The Institute of Trade Mark Agents (ITMA) has a large number of affiliated members countrywide:

ITMA

Canterbury House
2-6 Sydenham Road
Croydon
Surrey
CR0 9XE

Regional Contacts

Frequently it is beneficial to deal with local offices for advice, industrial contacts and funding for exploitation activities rather than use remote central offices which are often based in London. Development of exploitation partnerships will involve a good deal of communication so a local partner can save considerable time and money.

Regional contacts can be made by through the local **Business Links** Office which can be found through either the telephone directory, by contacting the local branch of

the Department of Trade and Industry or local Chamber of Commerce. A general contact number for the DTi is 0171 215 5000.

Business Links

Business Links are regional, independently limited companies with resident consultants who are both technically qualified in addition to having a strong business background. Their remit is to act as a focal point for both SMEs and service providers. They have been formed by partnerships between local TECs (Training Enterprise Council), Chambers of Commerce and local Councils. In addition to providing a local focal point Business Links also has access to Supernet, managed by Pera International which is a database of leading technology organisations such as Universities and Research Institutes.

Chamber of Commerce

Details of your nearest affiliated Chamber of Commerce can be obtained from:

The British Chambers of Commerce (BCC)

9 Tufton Street
London
SW1P 3QB
Tel: 0171 248 4444
Fax: 0171 489 0391

Partners for Exploitation

Exploitation may be available from a company which already sells a complementary *product* and has experience of the relevant markets. This will become evident during your review of the market. However, there are a number of other avenues that can be explored where it will be

possible to either sell or licence your IP to a second party in order for them to do the exploitation. Partners may be found through personal contacts or knowledge of a market sector, but there is another way, through a technology transfer company or a brokerage system.

❖ **BTG plc**

BTG is a well known example of a technology transfer company with wide experience of patenting and licensing technology to industry worldwide and has expertise in the protection, development and marketing of intellectual property.

BTG plc

101 Newington Causeway
London SE1 6BU
Tel: 0171 403 6666
Fax: 0171 403 7586

Technology Brokers/Intermediaries

In addition to the bodies which offer membership and support for inventors there is a growing number of intermediary companies who offer a service, for a fee, for matching projects with potential users, usually through a regularly published newsletter or directory. The directories contain listings of technology offers. See page 33 for details on how to write a technology offer.

❖ **Technology Innovation Information (TII)**

Publishes a directory of technology transfer and innovation support organisations from 30 countries. The directory is an invaluable source book for finding consultancy organisations qualified to tackle

a particular technology transfer or innovation assignment. TII run the Technology Response Network (TRN) which is a brokerage offering TII members a common service for circulating their technology offers and requests from their client companies to a network of suppliers and brokers.

TII asbl

3 rue des Capucins
L-1313 Luxembourg
Tel: (352) 46 30 35
Fax: (352) 46 21 85

NERC is a corporate member of TII and hence TRN.

❖ **International Innovation Sources**

IIS publishes a newsletter quarterly and charges (in 1995) £10 for the first three introductions for members and £15 per inquiry for non members. No further fees are required as a result of any successful exploitation.

IIS

Sheffield Technology Park
60 Shirland Lane
Sheffield S9 3SP
Tel: 01142 560 220
Fax: 01142 618 555

❖ **The Technology Broker**

The Technology Broker publishes "Portfolio" quarterly and also hosts the English Relay Centre, the focal point for exploitation of EU Research and Technology Development (RTD). The network seeks to locate partners, customers, licencees and/or manufacturers throughout Europe for organisations with a need. Fees vary according to

the deal that is put together.

The Technology Broker
 Station Road
 Longstanton
 Cambridge CB4 5DS
 Tel 01954 261199
 Fax 01954 260291

❖ **Technology Initiatives Ltd**

A consultancy which project manages multi-contractor research and technology programmes in the natural resource field from concept to completion. Although Technology Initiatives are involved in large scale projects they may be aware of user needs throughout the industry.

Technology Initiatives Ltd
 No 1 Studley House
 Tunbridge Wells
 Kent TN4 8XS
 Tel: 01892 540820
 Fax: 01892 540824

Industry Organisations

Organisations which represent market or industry sectors can provide information on potential partners through their membership database and may also be aware of individual companies, or groups of companies, who would be interested in forming partnerships for exploitation. There are a wide number of such organisations, in the first instance it may be worth contacting Technology Interaction Group at Swindon Office to try to identify a relevant organisation.

Other Useful Sources of Information

Directorate of Intellectual Property Rights (D/IPR)

D/IPR is contained within the Ministry of Defence and is staffed by scientists who are also fully trained British and European Patent Attorneys and they have previously provided excellent advice and services to NERC, for example the modification of aircraft for the Antarctic. The D/IPR covers a wide field of expertise developed over many years. Briefly they have specific experience in the following:

- ❖ Shared funding contracts and sponsorship arrangements.
- ❖ IPR arrangements for collaborative projects and information exchanges with industry, with other governments and with international agencies.
- ❖ Confidentiality agreements.
- ❖ EEC contract conditions.
- ❖ Enforcing UK government IP against infringers.
- ❖ Exploitation of IP by licence negotiation.

Contact address within D/IPR is:
 PO Box 70
 Stoke Gifford
 Bristol BS12 7JH
 Tel: 0117 913 2855

The Internet

The Internet offers a vast resource of information on every subject under the sun; Intellectual Property issues are no different. Although undoubtedly there is a wealth of information to be found there is a large amount of unwanted material to search through. One useful resource is the service provided by MicroPatent, a well established electronic publisher of worldwide patent

information. MicroPatent have extended their CD-ROM service by developing a World Wide Web site at :
<http://www.micropat.com>

The home page provides a self explanatory guide to the services and includes an extensive range of free searching options. For further details either browse the website or contact MicroPatent directly.

MicroPatent
 Ealing House
 33 Hangar lane
 London
 W5 3HW
 Tel: 0181 932 0540
 Fax: 0181 9320480

The UK Patent Office home page is located at:

<http://www.netwales.co.uk/ptoffice/index.htm>

This provides general information about the services provided by the Patent Office in addition to suggesting the wealth of information contained within the worlds' Patent databases.

The Patent Office Useful Enquiry Addresses

The official registration of intellectual property, although an extremely important method of protection, is not a prerequisite to exploitation and it should not be taken up lightly because it may not be necessary, but more importantly, because it can be extremely expensive to do and may tie up valuable resources. However, the Patent Office itself offers a wide range of advisory services. These services are detailed below under individual headings.

Patents	The Patent Office Cardiff Road Newport Gwent NP9 1RH Tel: 01633 814000
Designs	The Patent Office Designs Registry Chartist Tower Upper Dock Street Newport Gwent NP9 1DW Tel: 01633 814000 ext 5162
Copyright	Industrial Property and Copyright Dept Copyright Enquiries Hazlitt House 45 Southampton Buildings Chancery Lane London WC2A 1AR Tel: 0171 438 4778
Search and Advisory Service	The Patent Office Hazlitt House 45 Southampton Buildings Chancery Lane London WC2A 1AR Tel: 0171 438 4747
Trade/Service Marks	The Patent Office Trade Mark Enquiries Cardiff Road Newport Gwent NP9 1RH Tel: 01633 814709

Marketing, **The Patent Office**
Publicity and **Marketing, Publicity and Information**
Information **Service**
 Room 3Y31
 Cardiff Road
 Newport
 Gwent NP9 1RH
 Tel: 01633 813535
 Fax: 01633 813600

Reference Books and Patent Information

The British Science Reference and Information Service (SRIS) is at the same address as the London Patent Office, 45 Southampton Buildings, London, WC2A 1AW and has a comprehensive selection of scientific, technical, and business reference books including extensive information on patents and trademarks. The library is open to the general public. For further information about services and opening hours telephone the general enquiry line - 0171 412 7494.

Reading and Background Information on IP

There is a wide range of books available on Intellectual Property and related issues, from basic introductory texts to the complex law treatise. For example Blackwells currently have five shelves of titles in print. A couple of introductory titles are given in Appendix 5, for more detailed information a visit to the Science Reference Library in London is suggested.

Finance for Commercial Exploitation

Introduction

Converting an idea into a successful and marketable product requires effort, commitment and finance. Exploitation costs can be extremely high and can be met by the exploitation partner (when licensing) or by a finance body when you wish to do the exploitation yourself. **The principle aim of exploitation is to generate a profit.** Many *products* that have been developed as a result of commercial exploitation of NERC-IP have not made significant profits and indeed may have unknowingly lost money.

Exploitation planning must include a strategy for *product* development: improvement of the first generation *products*, new, and wider markets, development of improved second generation *products* and investment in further research or new equipment.

As with all NERC activities, exploitation should be approached with excellence in mind. In business terms, excellence or success can only be measured by the financial returns and job creation.

Product Definition

An essential first step is to define your *product*. This means that you will have to develop knowledge of the market into which you will launch your *product*. To maximise the chance of success and to reduce risks to a known and manageable level you should seek as much information about comparable *products* and services against which you will be competing. Details on companies offering competitive *products* will have to be obtained. The following basic questions must be answered:

- ❖ What size is the potential market? Is it a UK or worldwide market? Is it growing?
- ❖ What role does technology play in the market?
- ❖ Is the market changing rapidly?
- ❖ How many different manufacturers/vendors are there of similar *products*?
- ❖ Who will buy the *product*? Why will they buy the *product*?
- ❖ How much will it cost and how much will it sell for?
- ❖ What other similar *products* are there on the market?

Do not underestimate either the time or difficulty that may be involved with this part of the exercise. A successful assessment of the current market will be the key to the success of any exploitation. Experience suggests that most businesses fail because of incorrect assessment of the market and its size. Even if much of the business is to be undertaken by a partner in the private sector, you will still need to ensure that the partnership agreement generates appropriate benefits for NERC, for which an understanding of the business and the markets is a prerequisite. A good understanding of the market, whatever exploitation route you take, is important to give yourself a strong position in any negotiations.

Collection of Market Intelligence.

How market intelligence is collected will to some extent depend upon the *product* that you have in mind. Some suggestions are detailed below and a table is included in Appendix 3 to illustrate the aims of market information.

Be careful how much information about your IP and your commercial intentions you disclose to others without a confidentiality disclosure agreement being in place. This will be particularly important if you are talking to potential competitors. Market intelligence can be gathered by talking to a number of different organisations:

- ❖ Companies working in similar areas.
- ❖ Trade organisations.
- ❖ Other users.

Can you identify any features which are unique to your *product*, a unique selling point (USP), and are there any potential conflicts in IP such as with *product* names, logos, principles of the technique etc. which may result in litigation? Essentially this is the type of market research which must be done at an early stage of IP exploitation. It is a time when a search of current trademarks and *products* can be made either through the Patent Office or through a specialist company. Other sources of information can be obtained from:

- ❖ Competitors.
- ❖ Government statistics.
- ❖ Newspapers.
- ❖ Trade journals.
- ❖ Market research agencies.
- ❖ Trade/professional conferences, seminars.
- ❖ Technical literature.
- ❖ Periodicals.

You may wish to review all this information with Technology Interaction after you have collated it.

Your Competitors

Obtain a copy of the annual report of your competitors and their published accounts from Companies House or

directly from the company. Additionally, keep an eye on the business pages for details of companies operating in your market sector to help build up your picture of the market.

- ❖ *Product* range and size.
- ❖ Company turnover.
- ❖ Profits for the previous few years.
- ❖ Number of employees worldwide.
- ❖ Market size and market share.
- ❖ Share prices.

Once all of this information is collected together you will be able to identify your needs, assess the impact of the competition on your product(s) and market share and you should then be in a position to write a business plan which will help you to plot your next actions.

Risk Assessment

Whilst deciding on the appropriate exploitation route it is important to assess any qualitative and quantitative risks. Sound market intelligence will be invaluable in helping to minimise risks.

Development Programme and Costs

Sufficient time must be allocated to provide firm foundations for exploitation; in particular you should speak with other people who have relevant experience. Their help will be invaluable as they will enable you to consider all relevant issues. This will provide a clear idea of what needs to be done in terms of prototype development or production and testing of demonstration models. Additionally, this can provide information on any associated costs, some of which you may well have overlooked.

Proof of Concept

Work out a timetable for the development of the prototype, its testing and the manufacture of the first production model up to the point of the first sale. These costs should include the production of sales literature and support documentation as well as training of sales staff. These estimates have to be realistic and can be expressed in terms of the probability of success of each stage covering both elapsed time and expenditure incurred. This process may take several months, during which time you will need to have access to finances which will not require immediate payback; so-called "patient money". It is vitally important that this process be well managed ie, prudently and professionally. Any additional IP developed in this phase will be a clear demonstration to financial backers of progress being made and will, in part, act as a security for the finance being provided.

In many instances the aim will be to secure a partner from the private sector to take over the *product* development, but even so this will still probably require some input from yourself. In either case further funding will probably be required from an external source.

Funding for Exploitation

Inventors, Innovators and scientists working within institutions are generally paid to do science, not to exploit, and they rarely have sufficient funding to transfer their knowledge or prototype into a *product* that is marketable. Development and marketing costs can be extremely high in terms of:

- ❖ Protecting the intellectual property.
- ❖ Defending the intellectual property.
- ❖ Funding the development costs.
- ❖ Packaging and marketing the *product*.

There are a number of organisations that can assist with exploitation activities; they should not be approached in a random or haphazard manner. You should talk with your technology transfer /marketing office and develop an outline or draft business plan first.

Funding for Technology Transfer

Costs associated with transferring a product from the laboratory to a saleable product can easily equal or outweigh the costs of the initial research. A common practice to share the risk of transferring a research programme output into a *product* is to employ a specialist organisation such as:

British Technology Group
101 Newington Causeway
London SE1 6BU
Tel: 0171 403 6666
Fax: 0171 403 7586

Venture Scientifics Ltd
c/o High Trees
Temple Wood Lane
Stoke Poges
Bucks SL2 3HW
Tel: 01753 648090
Fax: 01753 648090

Oxford Innovation
Oxford Centre for Innovation
Mill Street
Oxford OX2 0JX
Tel: 01865 794585
Fax: 01865 209044

Funding for Development

Finance for developing a business in the early stages, when it is still too small to obtain backing from venture capitalists, may be obtained from private individuals or consortia, known as business angels. The British Venture Capital Association (BVCA) produces a directory, "Sources of Business Angel Capital" which contains details of how to contact business angels through either business introduction services or other networks. The finance is provided either by individuals or informal syndicates usually in return for an equity stake in the business. There are two key questions that should be asked before searching for informal equity from a business angel¹:

- ❖ Does my business have the potential to grow by 20% annually over a five year period?
- ❖ Am I prepared to accept that in order to achieve the growth potential of my company I will have to reduce my share of the equity?

An example of a business angel network is the Oxfordshire Investment Opportunity Network which is contactable at the same address as the Oxford Centre for Innovation (see above). Venture capital companies may be located either through the British Venture Capital Association or through your local Business Links office.

British Venture Capital Association
 Essex House
 12-13 Essex Street
 London WC2R 3AA
 Tel: 0171 240 3846
 Fax: 0171 240 3849

The completion of research and development projects is but one step in the overall commercial exploitation

process. In relative terms this phase is a low cost operation in comparison with design, engineering, production and sales activities which constitute the innovation process. Economic data compiled by the US Department of Commerce suggest that for every unit of cost in research and development three units are expended in design/engineering and 10 - 20 units, although this can be as high as 100, are expended in production and sales. These figures clearly indicate that the commercial potential of an invention or discovery can only be realised if significant investment is made.

An investor who has an interest in a piece of IP which is deemed to have commercial potential will wish to know the level of costs to be incurred in reaching the market place as well as the projected revenues arising from commercial exploitation.

In essence, the prime concern of any investor is an assurance that the investment will be well managed and the commercialisation process properly planned. This means that any proposal for external financial support should be written in the form of a business plan; indeed for support to be obtained from a venture capital company a business plan is essential. The following section is written as guidance on writing a business plan for submission to a venture capitalist, however it is equally applicable to a business plan being submitted to anybody else with access to finance. Probably the best known example of an investment body is:

Investors in Industry (3i)
 91 Waterloo Road
 London SE1 8XP
 Tel: 0171 928 3131

¹ Sources of Business Angel Capital 1994-95, British Venture Capital Association

Approaching a Venture Capitalist

The term "venture capital" usually refers to financial investment in unquoted companies which do not have access to traditional capital markets. Typically these companies are thought of as having high levels of risk and hence demand a high level of return. Such capital can be used to:

- ❖ Finance start-up companies.
- ❖ Help the expansion of an existing business into new markets.
- ❖ Rescue a failing business which has too much debt to service.
- ❖ Assist in the purchase of a business by management or another party.
- ❖ Restructure the balance sheet of a growing company.
- ❖ Finance new *product/process* development (rarely to fund research projects unless the market prospects are overwhelmingly attractive, eg new drugs).

It is important that anyone wishing to approach a source of venture capital appreciates that judgments will be made of the credibility of the management team, their commercial record and the assumptions underlying the business plan. Financiers always have far more proposals to consider than there are funds available and hence a technology plan must be exceptional to merit attention, analysis and support.

When seeking finance for a technology-based business it should be remembered that the potential financier is interested primarily in the returns to be made from a given investment rather than in the technology per se. Furthermore, the venture capitalist's perception of the associated risk will be biased by a general lay view among UK financiers that technology is risky and dangerous to

one's financial health.

The key to success therefore depends upon the preparation of a commercially viable business plan, which must not be disguised by scientific treatise, rather it must be a sound and credible exposé describing:

- ❖ Why the finance is needed.
- ❖ What the money will be used for.
- ❖ What returns will be gained over what period of time.

Related issues include the form of the finance sought (debt or equity - usually a mixture of the two), management role of the venture capital organization, sensitivity of the forecasts to change in external circumstances for example: *what if sales levels are lower than expected or quality standards vary?* Absolutely key issues will be the calibre and motivation of the management team and the exit route for the venture capitalist when the business has proved to be a success.

The Business Plan

The business plan must be regarded as being a crucially important document because you may only have one opportunity to present your ideas which will be competing with other proposals. This, in turn, means that the plan should be well researched, internally consistent and credible. A number of books and guides on how to write a business plan are available and each has its merits; a concise guide is *A Business Plan*, by Alan West, Pitman Publishing ISBN 0-273 61704-4, reprinted in 1995, cost about £6.50. This book is part of the NatWest Business Handbooks series.

Plans claiming that *new products* will gain 100% of a *new market* in less than two years with returns on

investment in excess of 50% are likely to be viewed with scepticism. Credible figures for competitive entry to an existing market with a new product will be much lower. The author(s) must be involved in the proposed new business and must fully understand the assumptions and implications of the plan so that its presentation will create a solid impression in the mind of the financier. This does not mean that external help should not be sought to write the business plan, but it should only be used as guiding support, not as a business plan production unit on the lines of professional editors of c.v.'s. The plan will inevitably be used to monitor progress of the business, particularly with reference to financial projections and, since you made them, you will probably be held to account for them at some future date and financial risk from you personally will be required in some form.

Business Plan Structure

Plans do not have to be lengthy: above all they should be comprehensible rather than comprehensive. A number of topics must be covered in the document so that your objectives and aims are clearly conveyed to the reader. A basic structure would be:

- ❖ Contents
- ❖ Executive summary (short - one page)
- ❖ Background (key business and technical points)
- ❖ *Product*
- ❖ Management
- ❖ Markets (size and quality)
- ❖ Operational aspects
- ❖ Financial details (and *what if...* scenarios)
- ❖ Target milestones
- ❖ Annexes

Executive Summary

The executive summary should be written very carefully since this may decide whether the document actually gets read. This overview should be aimed at stimulating the interest of and convincing the venture capitalist that it is worth taking the time to read the rest of the document.

Marketing and Management

Attention should also be paid to the sections on management and markets and in particular to the assumptions made on such topics as: the direction of the market and its likely growth rate, market share, role of competition, pricing strategy, etc.

Financial Plan

Experienced financiers will focus much of their attention on the assumptions underlying the plan, as the universal use of spreadsheets generally means that the financial arithmetic will be correct - the prime question will be: is it realistic? You must therefore state clearly what assumptions have been made in constructing your plan.

Final Format

The physical appearance of the business plan document is important and you should therefore include:

- a title page and author(s) name(s)
- number each copy and enclose an acknowledgment statement
- number all pages
- identify each section
- keep the sections brief and to the point
- avoid technical jargon and explain all technical terms: use a clear comprehensible language throughout

- consign all supporting evidence and information to the annex section
- date the proposal with the dispatch date.

The document should not be sent out as if it were a mail shot. Unsolicited documents tend not to be welcome. It is worth telephoning two or three venture capital firms known to have interests in a particular business area and briefly describe your proposal so that they can then request a copy of your plan. Advice on suitable firms can be obtained via TIG, who should be consulted in any case before committing resources to the preparation of a business plan.

Time Scale

The raising of financial support for a business or project plan is a selling operation and demands a high degree of professionalism. It is time consuming and negotiations can be tedious and difficult. Legal and tax advice will be needed as well as accounting input on the optimum financial structure. It is quite common for the total operation from conception of the business idea to signature on the financial offer document to take six months and it can take years, even if things go smoothly. All of these factors add up to the need for persistence and realism if the route to the market for your *product* is via the creation of a company.

Appraisal Methods for Investment Proposals

There are three main methods to appraise investment proposals:

- ❖ Return on investment.
- ❖ Pay back period.

- ❖ Discounted cash flow/net present value/internal rate of return.

They share the common characteristic of requiring the estimation of future benefits, expressing these in cash terms. Since these benefits arise over time it is important to recognise the change in value of cash with time. It is easy to quantify the investment amount but it is more difficult to estimate expenditure and income cash flow in real terms because of uncertainties in inflation and project progress.

Return on Investment (ROI)

This requires an estimation of average profits (total profit minus depreciation averaged over a set time period) and average investment (initial investment plus residual value averaged over the same time period as for the profits). This approach only takes account of profitability and ignores the time to reach any particular profit level.

Payback Period

In contrast to the profitability approach, this deals with the cash generated by the initial investment and essentially calculates the time to recover the investment. A common period for payback is established so that there is a standard for comparing all projects ie, investment to be recovered in "x" years, but if time exceeds "x" then the project will not be financed. When the investment is recovered then payback is irrelevant as no account is taken of future cash flows attributable to that investment.

Discounted Cash Flow (DCF)

This method overcomes the drawbacks of the above by

accounting for both profitability and the timing of cash flows. The basic principle is that cash now is of a greater value than the same amount to be received in the future. The crucial issue is the value of the discount factor to be applied to future cash so as to calculate its value today. As an illustration a discount rate of 15% will reduce £1000 by 0.5 in five years. The method requires the reduction of all future cash flows to a current value, known as Net Present Value (NPV).

Any appraisal method must be applied consistently within an organisation so that decision making in turn is consistent; without this, investment decisions are arbitrary or in reality become expenditure decisions.

Summary - Integration of Exploitation Activities

These guidance notes have described and informed on Intellectual Property and ways in which it may be taken to market. There are a number of steps involved in exploiting IP and for NERC to strengthen its performance in this area it is important for these steps to be integrated into all levels of the organisation and all levels of project planning and execution stages. By doing this, exploitation, or its consideration, will cease to be a difficult or onerous task.

The Technology Foresight Initiative and the creation of the Challenge Fund has provided a focus for NERC to re-appraise its strategy for Intellectual Property management and exploitation and has shown evidence of previous, not necessarily bad management, but neglect in these areas.

The publication of the Data Management Handbook in January 1996 and this Intellectual Property Management Handbook demonstrates how each individual in the NERC community can take an active part in the effective management of NERC IP. In summary the following points will help to avoid the problems of the past and will ensure that NERC can make a significant contribution to the Wealth Creation of the UK.

Identification

Early identification of IP with potential industrial applications can be improved in several ways:

- ❖ Proposals for new research projects should include indications of the potential commercial applications of the research results. Those involved in the research are more likely to recognise applications of emerging IP if they have already given some

initial consideration to likely outputs with industrial uses.

- ❖ Outputs from Technology Foresight exercises provide initial guidance about obvious user communities for specific areas of research.
- ❖ Scientists with industrial experience should participate in the research project.
- ❖ Early market research or intelligence should be obtained to enable the understanding of the needs of the more obvious industrial users of the research results.

Ownership

NERC does a substantial amount of research that is either funded or commissioned by other organisations. NERC's ability to capitalise on this IP is greatly affected by the IP exploitation arrangements agreed with these other organisations.

Contractual arrangements for Intellectual Property Rights from commissioned research must be secured before undertaking any sponsored or commissioned research.

Exploitation

There is wide recognition that the commercial exploitation of science and technology occurs most effectively when the process of research and discovery is in parallel with marketing and other commercial efforts which start early in the research cycle.

- ❖ Exploitation plans should evolve by simultaneous evaluation of likely research outcomes and market potential.

- ❖ Research can be altered or supplemented as opportunities for the creation and development of commercially valuable IP become apparent.
- ❖ Fundamental advances are more likely to occur when interaction between scientists, industrialists and technologists is high.

Protection

All staff must be aware of the need for prudence when disseminating research results. The timing of disclosing scientific results and undertaking actions to secure adequate IP protection can affect IP exploitation success. Public dissemination of IP through a lecture or paper or any other form ensures that patent protection and the protection afforded by confidential information can no longer be provided.

Scientists undertaking research funded by external organisations need to be exceptionally careful not to jeopardise the ability to protect IP by disseminating results too quickly. Contractual arrangements with these external organisations will almost always stimulate procedures that must be followed before dissemination can occur. Not following these procedures could place NERC in breach of contract and liable for damages.

Education and Training

In order that NERC can effectively manage its IP it is important that each individual understands what Intellectual Property is and acquires an understanding of its potential value. These notes will aid this learning process. However, to ensure that this learning process is undertaken, the responsibility for IP management should, to whatever extent line managers feel is relevant, be incorporated into the job description of each individual.

Appendix I: Examples of NERC's Intellectual Property

Data Holdings of NERC

A significant part of NERC's research activities results in the creation of datasets. In many cases, the data holdings and collections are *live* in the sense that they are continuously being updated, managed and validated.

These datasets are the *working tools* of active scientific groups. Other databases result from completed research projects and have been retained in archives.

NERC's databases have potential value because they yield some of the most comprehensive environmental information available (eg complete national coverage, long time series). Examples of valuable datasets held by NERC include:

- ❖ **The National River Flow Archive:** an accumulation of records from over a thousand observation stations and sites throughout the UK. Earliest records in the archive date from 1852.
- ❖ **The North Sea Project Data Set:** this comprises oceanographic data collected in the southern North Sea during the project's 1988-1991 field programme.
- ❖ **Borehole Record Archive:** BGS is both owner and/or custodian of almost one million borehole records in the UK.

Datasets are of vital importance to NERC's own core programmes as well as of great scientific and public service benefit. Additionally, datasets are also likely to be one of NERC's most commercially valuable form of Intellectual Property.

Computer Programs

NERC Institutes are active in the design of specialised computer programs which are developed to facilitate scientific research. These specialist software programs may have applications beyond that of the immediate requirements of NERC scientists. Opportunities therefore exist for their commercial exploitation.

Examples of software developed by NERC and currently being marketed to industry are:

- ❖ **POLPRED:** a PC based prediction program for calculating offshore tidal elevations and depth-averaged currents based on the results of a numerical model developed at the Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory.
- ❖ **GRAVMAG:** developed by the British Geological Survey, it is a gravity and magnetic modelling program that allows the user to visualise the information in 2.5 dimensions.

Maps - Spatially Referenced Data

NERC's research is focused on understanding the natural environment; this in consequence produces spatially related data sets; the collation and interpretation of these results in the production of maps, both in hard copy and in digital form, which is an extremely important mechanism for representing the conclusions of research investigations. These maps cover a diverse range of topics including:

- ❖ Solid Geology
- ❖ Sea-Bed Sediments
- ❖ Quaternary Geology

- ❖ Aeromagnetic Anomaly.
- ❖ Bouguer Gravity Anomaly.
- ❖ Critical Loads for Acidity of Soils in the United Kingdom.
- ❖ Land Classification of UK.

Technological advances in data manipulation and the ability to measure and predict the make up of the environment allows NERC's maps to continually evolve and to increase in value as they provide closer reflection of reality. The creation of higher resolution, and more robust, maps can result in them becoming valuable tools for an activity not previously envisaged. This can involve the amalgamation of different data sets and thus lead to further problems with ownership. The NERC Data Management Policy Document of January 1996 provides further guidance.

Innovative Devices

NERC has a successful record in developing observational instrumentation and equipment that enable new, improved and more efficient measurements to be made in support of its research projects. These include:

- ❖ A sea-bed mounted Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ACDP) which can measure turbulent structure in boundary layers.
- ❖ A pc-based digital seismic recording system.
- ❖ A long range side-scan sonar mapping system.
- ❖ A near sea-bed instrument to elucidate sediment erosion, transport and deposition.
- ❖ A Surface Capacitance Insertion Probe (SCIP) suitable for measuring water content at the surface

of soil.

- ❖ Multi Year Return Tide Level Equipment (MYRTLE) an improved version for the modernisation of the UK permanent tide gauge network.
- ❖ An autonomous underwater vehicle (AUTOSUB) for active deep ocean floor exploration and observation.

Innovative Processes

NERC is active in devising new procedures and methods for the advancement of scientific research, illustrated by the following examples:

- ❖ DML and IFE have developed carefully controlled methods of cultivating cultures of Algae and Protozoa. Devising improved methods for scaling up production of selected strains is integral to the industrial exploitation of the culture collection.
- ❖ IVEM have developed a process for producing blue tongue virus proteins. These are instrumental in the development of viral vaccines for protecting sheep against blue tongue infection.

Good practice within NERC should be based on a combination of a sound management process beginning with IP identification and including the appropriate assessment of the commercial potential of any particular item of IP.

Prediction Tools

Increasingly, the requirements of the NERC user

community are becoming more demanding, one clear message is that they don't want data, they want information in a form which is easy to understand and easy to apply. Frequently this involves not simply presenting a single dataset, but combining several datasets with predictive models into a form which can produce useful, relevant and accessible information. Examples of predictive tools developed by NERC are:

- ❖ **RIVPACS is an acronym for River Prediction And Classification System.** It is a method for predicting the expected macro-invertebrate fauna (mainly insect larvae and worms) at a site in a river. This allows a comparison with actual data obtained by sampling the river in a standard way. The difference between predicted and observed is used to classify the site according to its biological quality. It is a standard methodology in use with the Environment Agency which IFE / FBA developed.
- ❖ **Pollution HAZard Estimation System.** Developed for the insurance and re-insurance industry from NERC data holdings PHAZES deals

with the hazard liability arising from new pollution incidents which are likely to give rise to environmental contamination; the effect of the incident can vary significantly depending upon the site. PHAZES provides insurers with information on grid referenced or post coded locations which is critical to their understanding of the risk involved with individual liabilities. PHAZES is licensed to Chapman Hall.

- ❖ **GHASP (Geo Hazard Susceptibility Package)** is the registered tradename of a family of hazard susceptibility products, aimed initially at the UK insurance industry. GHASP was conceived by BGS as a digital information package to aid the insurance underwriter in assessing the risk from natural, subsidence-inducing hazards when fixing domestic building insurance rates. The data are provided as averages at the postcode sector level, as a significant refinement to the dominantly postcode area based ratings common at the time of its first release. GHASP 1 consists of maps and a database which are both updated regularly.

Appendix 2: The Patent Process

1. **Describe how your idea/product is unique or useful.**
2. **Why are you thinking of patenting?**
3. **Who funded the work and what did the original contract say about Intellectual Property?**

This section will help to prepare you to talk with a patent agent.

Title of the Invention (suggest what the invention will do, not the way that it will do it).

Field (or fields) of Invention (areas in which you envisage the invention will find application).

Statement of the Invention.

Background - what is relevant to your invention that is currently in the public domain.

The problem addressed or solved by your invention.

Description of the Invention (describe the invention in detail using jargon free language, include as many figures, photographs or diagrams as necessary).

Benefits (describe the benefits of the invention and how it overcomes the disadvantages currently encountered).

Can/will your invention lead to other perturbations? Indicate any other examples or alternative forms of the invention currently, or soon to be, available.

Consider the geographic area over which it is important to have patent protection. List the drawings, photographs and diagrams attached.

4. **Talk with a patent agent.**

Review your application.

Further development/testing/understanding may be required.

5. **File your application** (usually £500 to £3000 depending upon the complexity) and establish "priority date" this gives 12 months protection to strengthen your patent, provide further evidence that it works and to find a licensee.
6. **Preliminary examination** and search producing a search report: Search fee is required. This can be done at any time prior to the full examination and will permit amendments to be made to the patent.
7. Publication of application.
8. **Second filing** requires some more finance and some decisions such as the level of coverage required.
9. Substantive examination - requires a further fee within six months of publication.
10. Examiner's response - possible to make amendments/present arguments to overcome problems.
11. Patent Granted: this can take several years.

NOTE:

Exploitation can take place at any time during the patent application stage.

Confidentiality is essential before first filing and ideally should be maintained further. Discuss this with your patent agent.

To avoid inconveniences, the possibility of filing should be reviewed frequently during research.

Appendix 3: Market Information

Transforming your idea into a successful product is an iterative process of information gathering and evaluation of the product form and function, the market and the competition during development, formation of partnerships and when seeking finance.

	Information requirement	Development	Partnerships	Finance
Product	Understanding the product			
	What is it? What will it do? Who will want it? and why? How many will want it? and at what price?			
People	Understanding the customer			
	Customer profile Market sector information Customer specific requirements Decision making process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● who makes the decision? ● what are the criteria? ● who holds the budgets? ● what is currently used? ● what is it worth? 			
Price	Understanding the competition			
	Selling price Product portfolio/range Historic market profile Sales trends Product profitability			
Promotion	Promotional Plan			
	Assess relevant media Target market, type and distribution Budget Next product			
Evaluation	Monitor Marketing			
	Customer feedback Sales trends Competitor actions			
Operational	Customer Communication			
	Complaints/Suggestions Individual needs/Specific requests			
	Implement Marketing Plan			
	Product information Distributor information Terms and conditions of sale			

Appendix 4: Intellectual Property/Marketing Network

Centre/Survey	Contact	Phone No.
BAS	Dougal Goodman	01223 251253
BGS	Jean Alexander	0115 936 3331
DML	Jim Watson	01631 567877
IFE	John Hilton	01929 462314
IH	Neil Runnalls	01491 692373
ITE (Edinburgh)	Bob Munro	0131 445 4343
ITE (Furzebrook)	Nigel Webb	01929 551087
ITE (Monkswood)	Sue Wallis/Tim Moffat	01487 773381
IVEM	Joanna Sloley	01865 512361
PML	Peter Claridge	01752 633112
POL	Graham Alcock	0151 653 8633
SOC	Dave Billet	01703 596101
Swindon (TIG)	Jan Peters	01793 411764

Appendix 5: Useful Publications

An Introduction to Intellectual Property Law by Jeremy Philips and Alison Firth, Butterworths 1990, ISBN 0 406 51240 X.

Intellectual Property and the Academic Community, published March 1995, available from The Royal Society, 6 Carlton House Terrace, London, SW1Y 5AG, ISBN 0 85403 496 X.

The Patent Office has a range of publicity material which ranges from leaflets and booklets to videos.

Intellectual Property, by David I Bainbridge, published by Pitman, ISBN 0 273 60422 8, published in 1994, cost about £20. Standard Law textbook aimed at students with comprehensive coverage of all types of IP with understandable case studies and explanations.

The Innovators Source Book 1995 (ISBN 0 9520908 2 1) is published by Tweedprint Ltd Tel 01257 427 332. This contains a listing of companies and services involved in innovation and intellectual property exploitation in addition to a series of articles and adverts and may be worth consulting. The book retails for £20 in 1995, and is published yearly.

A Business Plan, by Alan West, Pitman Publishing ISBN 0-273 61704-4, reprinted in 1995, cost about £6.50. This book is part of the NatWest Business Handbooks series.

Valuation of Intellectual Property and Intangible Assets by Gordon V Smith and Russel L Parr, Second Edition, published by John Wiley and Sons 1995.

Technology Transfer, Making the Most of your Intellectual Property, by Neil F Sullivan, Cambridge University Press, 1995, ISBN 0 521 46616 4.

Intellectual Property in Industry by T Black, published by Butterworths, ISBN 0 406 10140 X.

Licensing Checklists by D Edmunds Brazell, published by Kenneth Mason Publications Ltd, ISBN 0 85937 347 9.

Commercial Exploitation of Intellectual Property by Hilary Pearson and Clifford Miller, published by Blackstone Press Ltd, ISBN 1 85431 044 5.